

FUNCTIONAL PEARL

Longest r-chain: thinning by grouping

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1 Introduction

Poetition is a popular game show that revolves around poems and poetry. In the opening quiz, contestants have to guess a poem from a few letters, for example, *hikhhllnrspomlostr*. All you know is that the letters appear in the same order as in the poem. In particular, the letters need not be adjacent. The example is a formidable challenge, but perhaps you have an idea of what the poem might be?

Looking behind the scenes, the clues are generated mechanically — they are so-called *r*-chains. Let *r* be some relation on elements. An *r*-chain is a sequence of elements such that adjacent elements are related by *r*: if *a* is followed by *b*, then *r a b* must hold (but not necessarily *r b a*). In the example above, two characters are related if they are close neighbours in the Unicode character set.

```
close :: Int -> (Char -> Char -> Bool)
close d a b = abs (ord a - ord b) <= d
```

The first argument specifies the admissible distance between the characters *a* and *b*. In *hikhhllnrspomlostr*, characters are at most 4 positions apart. In fact, the clue is the *longest subsequence* (of the first two lines) of the to-be-guessed poem that satisfies this property. A subsequence is given by removing zero or more characters from the original poem.

```
> longest-chain (close 4) . unlines . take 2 . lines . poem
"hikhhllnrspomlostr"
```

Note that the dot “.” denotes right-associating function application, whereas we use a circle “◦” for function composition (not used above): $f . g . x = f . g x = f (g x) = (f \circ g) x$.

By choosing *r* appropriately, one can reveal different pieces of information. In general, the larger the relation, the longer the clue:

$$r \subseteq s \implies \text{length} (\text{longest-chain } r \text{ } xs) \leq \text{length} (\text{longest-chain } s \text{ } xs).$$

If we set the distance to, say, 13, then the poem is almost completely uncovered.

```
> longest-chain (close 13) . unlines . take 2 . lines . poem
"thinkthtshallneereepoemlovllystree"
```


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Alternative choices for r include (partial) equivalence relations; for example, *both* p relates two elements if they both satisfy the property p .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{both} &:: (\text{char} \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow (\text{char} \rightarrow \text{char} \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \\ \text{both } p \ a \ b &= p \ a \ \wedge \ p \ b \end{aligned}$$

For this choice, the clue contains all the characters that belong to the same character class.

```
> longest-chain (both vowel) . unlines . take 2 . lines . poem
"IiaIaeeeeAoeoeaaee"
```

Ordering relations give rise to even more challenging clues.

```
> longest-chain (<) . unlines . take 2 . lines . poem
"Thiklnrsvy"
```

So much for the motivation. The purpose of this pearl is to derive an efficient algorithm for computing longest r -chains, generalizing the “longest increasing subsequence” problem, which requires r to be a total preorder. The final program is, in fact, asymptotically optimal.

2 Specification

Here is a possible specification of the function *longest-chain*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{longest-chain} &:: (\text{char} \rightarrow \text{char} \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow [\text{char}] \rightarrow [\text{char}] \\ \text{longest-chain } r &= \text{longest} \circ \text{filter } (\text{chain } r) \circ \text{sublists} \end{aligned}$$

The composite structure is typical of optimization problems: a generator is followed by a filter, which in turn is followed by the “target” function. Note that *char* is a type variable — we abstract away from the character set.

The target function *longest* selects the first string with maximum length. (For simplicity, we assume that *length* runs in constant time. Making this assumption true is a routine optimization.)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{type } \text{Alt } a &= [a] \\ \text{longest} &:: \text{Alt } [\text{char}] \rightarrow [\text{char}] \\ \text{longest} &= \text{foldr } (\uparrow) [] \text{ where } w \uparrow x = \text{if } \text{length } w \geq \text{length } x \text{ then } w \text{ else } x \end{aligned}$$

Lists are ubiquitous in functional programming. It is useful to distinguish sequences $[A]$ from collections of choices *Alt* A , although we will represent both by lists.

The predicate *chain* r determines whether its argument is an r -chain.¹

$$\begin{aligned} \text{chain} &:: (\text{char} \rightarrow \text{char} \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow ([\text{char}] \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \\ \text{chain } r \ w &= \text{and } (\text{zipWith } r \ w \ (\text{tail } w)) \end{aligned}$$

Finally, *sublists* returns all subsequences of a list and can be defined inductively by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sublists} &:: [\text{char}] \rightarrow \text{Alt } [\text{char}] \\ \text{sublists} &= \text{foldr } (\oplus) [[]] \text{ where } a \oplus ws = \text{map } (a:) \ ws \ ++ \ ws \end{aligned}$$

Observe that the length of the resulting list is doubled in each step: there are 2^n subsequences of a list of length n . Consequently, even though the specification is executable, it is not very practical as it requires exponential time.

¹The definition is standard, but subtle: even though *tail* is undefined for empty lists, *tail* $[] = \perp$, the predicate is total, in particular, *chain* r $[] = \text{True}$ as *zipWith* is non-strict in the second argument, *zipWith* f $[] \ \perp = []$.

3 Thinning by grouping

Open the program calculation toolbox. As the generator *sublists* is given by a fold, we might try to apply *foldr*-fusion.

$$f (\text{foldr } (\oplus) n xs) = \text{foldr } (\otimes) e xs \quad \Leftarrow \quad \begin{cases} f n = e & \text{(base)} \\ f (x \oplus s) = x \otimes f s & \text{(step)} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Fusing *longest* \circ *filter* (*chain* r) with *sublists* is, however, bound to fail. To see why, suppose there is an operation (\otimes) satisfying the step-condition. Consider the input "abcxy" and assume that there are two r -chains "abc" and "xy", and that no other elements are related by r . We calculate

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{"abc"} \\ = & \{ \text{assumption: "abc" is the longest } r\text{-chain of "abcxy"} \} \\ & \text{longest-chain "abcxy"} \\ = & \{ \text{longest-chain} = \text{foldr } (\otimes) [] \} \\ & \text{foldr } (\otimes) [] \text{"abcxy"} \\ = & \{ \text{definition of foldr} \} \\ & 'a' \otimes ('b' \otimes (\text{foldr } (\otimes) [] \text{"cxy"})) \\ = & \{ \text{longest-chain} = \text{foldr } (\otimes) [] \} \\ & 'a' \otimes ('b' \otimes (\text{longest-chain "cxy"})) \\ = & \{ \text{assumption: "xy" is the longest } r\text{-chain of "cxy"} \} \\ & 'a' \otimes ('b' \otimes \text{"xy"}) \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, there is no such (\otimes) so that "abc" = 'a' \otimes ('b' \otimes "xy") because (\otimes) cannot recover 'c'. In other words, the problem of longest r -chains does not exhibit optimal substructure, whereby optimal solutions to a problem incorporate optimal solutions to substructures.

This sounds like a clear case for *thinning* [1]. Thinning is a general technique for solving optimization problems where the best solution is selected from a set of candidate solutions. The technique comes into play, if

- a *brute-force* solution, which considers all candidates, is too costly — in our case, there are 2^n different subsequences of a list of length n ; and
- a *greedy* solution, where only a single candidate is maintained, does not work — the problem of longest uptrend does not exhibit optimal substructure.

Such a subset is not too hard to find. Assume that a is some letter of the to-be-guessed poem and consider all the candidates that start with a . These candidates stand or fall together: either all of them are extendable at the front or none of them is — recall that *foldr* dictates that partial solutions are extended at the front. Consequently, we only need to keep the longest.

How can we turn this insight into code? As a first step in this direction, we define a variant of *sublists* that *groups* the candidates by the first character. These groups are then grouped recursively by the second letter, and so forth. Tries enter the scene.

4 Multitries

Tries were introduced by the Norwegian mathematician Axel Thue in 1912 as a means to represent *sets* of strings. A trie is a multiway branching tree where each edge is labelled with a character. For example, the set of strings $\{ear, earl, east, easy, egg, eye\}$ is given by the trie shown below.

Each path from the root to a marked node, drawn as a filled circle, represents a string: simply concatenate the labels of the edges. Above, *eye* is a member of the set, but neither *ey* nor *e* is.

For the application at hand, we can simplify things a little bit: since the set of all subsequences is closed under taking prefixes, we do not need to distinguish between different node types. So a node is simply a list of labelled edges leading to its children.

```

type Node label = [ Edge label ]
data Edge label = label :=> Node label
label :: Edge label -> label
label (k :=> v) = k

```

An edge is depicted by a so-called maplet $k :=> v$ (inspired by Z notation), which represents a pair of a label k leading to a node v . Since an element can occur several times in a sequence, there may be several edges coming out of the same node that are labelled with the same character. So a more appropriate name for the datastructure is perhaps *multitrie*. A standard trie represents a *set* of strings; the outgoing edges form a finite map from labels to subtrees. Our tries represent *lists* of strings; the outgoing edges form a multimap, hence the proposed name.

Building on multitries, an alternative specification of the function *longest-chain* reads:

```

longest-chain :: (char -> char -> Bool) -> [char] -> [char]
longest-chain r = longest-path o filter-path r o trie-of-sublists

```

(2)

The generator returns a trie of all subsequences; the filter ensures that every path from the root to any node is an r -chain, from which the target function selects the longest. Creating a trie is more direct than creating a list of all subsequences.

```

trie-of-sublists :: [label] -> Node label
trie-of-sublists = foldr (⊕) [] where a ⊕ v = (a :=> v) : v

```

The computation $\text{map } (a:) \text{ ws} ++ \text{ws}$ is turned into data $(a :=> v) : v$. The representation change has a dramatic impact on the running time: due to sharing of subtrees, the generator now runs in linear time! But it is too early to celebrate, because every subsequent operation destroys the sharing.

As an aside, the generated multitrie has a very characteristic shape. For example, the list of subsequences of *abcd* is represented by

We obtain a so-called *binomial tree*. The number of nodes on each level — that is, the number of subsequences of the same length — is given by a binomial coefficient. We have not attempted to visualize sharing, but it is evident that the tree contains many repeated subtrees; in particular, the first subtree of the root is identical to its tail.

The types *Node* and *Edge* are defined by mutual recursion. Function follows form: adapting *filter (chain r)* to multitries results in two functions defined by mutual recursion.

```

filter-path :: (label → label → Bool) → (Node label → Node label)
filter-path r = map (filter-via r)
filter-via :: (label → label → Bool) → (Edge label → Edge label)
filter-via r (a :=> u) = a :=> filter-path r [b :=> v | (b :=> v) ← u, r a b]
    
```

The filter predicate *chain r* is now built in: we make sure that the labels of two successive edges are related by r . For the following calculations it is preferable to desugar the list comprehension: we have $[b :=> v \mid (b :=> v) \leftarrow u, r a b] = \text{filter } (r a \circ \text{label}) u$.

Finally, *longest-path* determines the longest path in a trie. If there are several paths of the same length, it picks the first one.

```

longest-path :: Node label → [label]
longest-path = longest ◦ map longest-via
longest-via :: Edge label → [label]
longest-via (a :=> v) = a : longest-path v
    
```

The energetic reader may want to show that the two specifications are equivalent. To this end, we introduce an abstraction function that maps the new representation to the old representation. Note that the empty sequence $[\]$ is always included in the list of subsequences. This is necessarily the case as, in contrast to standard tries, all nodes are marked and the empty path leads to the root node.

```

abstr :: Node char → Alt [char]
abstr v = concat (map edge v) ++ [[]]
edge :: Edge char → Alt [char]
edge (a :=> v) = map (a.) (abstr v)
    
```

Multitries factor out common prefixes: all strings in $a :=> v$ start with an a . The function *edge* explodes the compact representation.

Generators, filters, and target functions are related by:

$$\text{abstr} \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} = \text{sublists} \quad (3a)$$

$$\text{abstr} \circ \text{filter-path } r = \text{filter } (\text{chain } r) \circ \text{abstr} \quad (3b)$$

$$\text{longest-path} = \text{longest} \circ \text{abstr} \quad (3c)$$

Once these laws are established, showing that the two specifications coincide is a breeze.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{longest} \circ \text{filter } (\text{chain } r) \circ \text{sublists} \\ = & \{ \text{introduce } \text{trie-of-sublists} \text{ (3a)} \} \\ & \text{longest} \circ \text{filter } (\text{chain } r) \circ \text{abstr} \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \\ = & \{ \text{introduce } \text{filter-path} \text{ (3b)} \} \\ & \text{longest} \circ \text{abstr} \circ \text{filter-path } r \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \\ = & \{ \text{introduce } \text{longest-path} \text{ (3c)} \} \\ & \text{longest-path} \circ \text{filter-path } r \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \end{aligned}$$

5 Derivation

Now, we can let the symbols do the work. Starting with the second specification (2), we first we plug in some definitions.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{longest-path} \circ \text{filter-path } r \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \\ = & \{ \text{definition of } \text{longest-path} \} \\ & \text{longest} \circ \text{map } \text{longest-via} \circ \text{filter-path } r \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \\ = & \{ \text{definition of } \text{filter-path} \} \\ & \text{longest} \circ \text{map } \text{longest-via} \circ \text{map } (\text{filter-via } r) \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \\ = & \{ \text{second functor law: } \text{map} \text{ preserves composition} \} \\ & \text{longest} \circ \text{map } (\text{longest-via} \circ \text{filter-via } r) \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \end{aligned}$$

The final expression captures the idea of thinning by grouping. The composite

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{longest-chains} :: (\text{char} \rightarrow \text{char} \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow [\text{char}] \rightarrow \text{Alt } [\text{char}] \\ & \text{longest-chains } r = \text{map } f \circ \text{trie-of-sublists} \textbf{ where } f = \text{longest-via} \circ \text{filter-via } r \end{aligned}$$

computes the thinned subset, well, sublist: for each *occurrence* of a character in the to-be-guessed poem it contains the longest r -chain starting with that character. The longest of these candidates is then the best solution. Our goal is to derive an efficient implementation of *longest-chains*. Since the generator is given by a fold, we appeal to *foldr*-fusion (1). There are two proof obligations: For the base values (1–base) there is little to do: the definition of *map* immediately gives $\text{map } f [] = []$. For the step function (1–step), we need to calculate an operator (\otimes) satisfying $\text{map } f (a \oplus v) = a \otimes \text{map } f v$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{map } f (a \oplus v) \\ = & \{ \text{definition of } \oplus \} \\ & \text{map } f ((a \mapsto v) : v) \\ = & \{ \text{definition of } \text{map} \} \\ & f (a \mapsto v) : \text{map } f v \end{aligned}$$

To reduce clutter, we focus on the head. The goal is clear: we need to rewrite $f (a \mapsto v)$ into an expression that involves $\text{map } f \ v$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& f (a \mapsto v) \\
= & \{ \text{definition of } f \} \\
& \text{longest-via} . \text{filter-via } r (a \mapsto v) \\
= & \{ \text{definition of } \text{filter-via} \} \\
& \text{longest-via} (a \mapsto \text{filter-path } r . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{definition of } \text{filter-path} \} \\
& \text{longest-via} (a \mapsto \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . v)
\end{aligned}$$

The application of map after filter smells like a case for the map-filter swap rule.

$$\text{map } f \ \circ \ \text{filter} (p \ \circ \ f) = \text{filter } p \ \circ \ \text{map } f \tag{4}$$

Our combination of map and filter does not quite match the left-hand side of the rule but a simple observation saves the day: $\text{filter-via } r$ does not change the label of the root.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \text{longest-via} (a \mapsto \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{label} \ \circ \ \text{filter-via } r = \text{label} \} \\
& \text{longest-via} (a \mapsto \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label} \ \circ \ \text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{map-filter swap rule (4)} \} \\
& \text{longest-via} (a \mapsto \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{definition of } \text{longest-via} \} \\
& a : (\text{longest-path} . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{definition of } \text{longest-path} \} \\
& a : (\text{longest} . \text{map } \text{longest-via} \ \circ \ \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . v)
\end{aligned}$$

A second opportunity for applying the map-filter swap rule arises. Again, we first need to massage the filter predicate.

$$\begin{aligned}
& a : (\text{longest} . \text{map } \text{longest-via} \ \circ \ \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{label}) . \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{head} \ \circ \ \text{longest-via} = \text{label} \} \\
& a : (\text{longest} . \text{map } \text{longest-via} \ \circ \ \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{head} \ \circ \ \text{longest-via}) . \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{map-filter swap rule (4)} \} \\
& a : (\text{longest} . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{head}) . \text{map } \text{longest-via} \ \circ \ \text{map} (\text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{second functor law: } \text{map} \ \text{preserves composition} \} \\
& a : (\text{longest} . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{head}) . \text{map} (\text{longest-via} \ \circ \ \text{filter-via } r) . v) \\
= & \{ \text{definition of } f \} \\
& a : (\text{longest} . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{head}) . \text{map } f \ v)
\end{aligned}$$

Voilà! The step function of the fused foldr reads:

$$a \otimes ws = (a : (\text{longest} . \text{filter} (r \ a \ \circ \ \text{head}) . ws)) : ws \tag{5}$$

We filter out the candidates that can be prefixed with a and then select the longest of these. Rather miraculously, the tries disappeared from the scene: *foldr*-fusion effectively deforests the intermediate data structure of tries.

6 Implementation

We have derived the following program for computing longest r -chains.

```

longest-chain :: (char → char → Bool) → [char] → [char]
longest-chain r = longest ∘ longest-chains r
longest-chains :: (char → char → Bool) → [char] → Alt [char]
longest-chains r = foldr (⊗) []
  where a ⊗ ws = (a : longest [b : w | (b : w) ← ws, r a b]) : ws

```

For readability, we have changed the filter (5) back to a list comprehension. Note that *longest-chains* returns a list of *non-empty* strings. Hence the pattern on the left-hand side of the generator $(b : w) \leftarrow ws$ never fails.

It is instructive to consider some example calls.

```

> longest-chains (close 4) "think"
["t", "hik", "ik", "nk", "k"]
> map head it
"think"
> longest-chains (λa b → succ a == b) "abcdxyz"
["abcd", "bcd", "cd", "d", "xyz", "yz", "z"]

```

Note that the derivation preserves the sharing present in the generator: $a \oplus v = (a : \mapsto v) : v$. In the trie, we share data; in the final program, we share computations; the calculation leads naturally from one to the other. The recursion pattern of *longest-chains* is, in fact, an instance of course-of-values recursion: the step function (5) has the form $a \otimes ws = g a ws : ws$ with $g a ws = a : longest [b : w | (b : w) \leftarrow ws, r a b]$.

Since f runs in linear time, *longest-chains r* exhibits a quadratic running-time. Can we do better than that? Clearly, the optimal running time depends on the relation:

- if r is the universal relation, $r a b = True$, then *longest-chain r* is the identity, which is a constant-time operation;
- if r is *both p* for some p , then *longest-chain r* simplifies to *filter p* (as *chain (both p)* is equivalent to *all p*), which runs in linear time;
- if r is a (partial) equivalence relation, *longest-chain r* can be made to run $\Theta(n \cdot k)$ time where k is the number of “different” characters in the input, that is, the number of equivalence classes;
- if r is a total preorder (strict or non-strict), the problem of longest r -chains specializes to the *longest increasing subsequence problem*, whose complexity is known to be $\Theta(n \cdot \log n)$ [3].

Alas, *longest-chains* is a higher-order function so the relation is a black box, an oracle. We can call the oracle, but not inspect it. Consider a one-point relation over the naturals: $r a b = a == x \wedge b == y$ for some fixed x and y with $0 \leq x, y < n$. The longest r -chain of the list $[0, 1, \dots, n-1, n-1, n-2, \dots, 1, 0]$ is $[x, y]$. But to determine the “unknowns” x and y , we need to call the oracle a quadratic number of times. Consequently, the problem complexity of

longest r -chains is quadratic and our implementation is asymptotically optimal. As an aside, the algorithm is often presented as a simple, but slow solution to the “longest increasing subsequence” problem. A key insight is that the algorithm actually solves a more general problem, and that this problem has no faster solution.

7 Conclusion

Every interesting program derivation contains an element of surprise. Our calculation begins with a surprise: the shocking suggestion to dispense with lists. To implement the idea of thinning by grouping we favoured a representation change: sequences of words are not represented by lists of lists of characters, but by a custom datatype that carves out the inherent structure: multitries. Although the final program does not use tries, they are essential to organize the derivation. We are not aware of any previous uses of (multi-) tries in program calculations, perhaps because tries are primarily seen as lookup structures. The problem of longest r -chains makes a compelling case for their usefulness.

The *thinning strategy* was introduced in the textbook “Algebra of Programming” by [1], albeit in a relational setting. It revolves around a relation $thin (\preceq): P A \leftarrow P A$. The preorder $\preceq: A \leftarrow A$ captures the essential algorithmic idea: $a \preceq b$ expresses that the candidate a is covered by the candidate b and need not be maintained. There are rules for introducing and eliminating $thin$ and several laws governing the interaction with other combinators. The recent textbook “Algorithm Design with Haskell” by [2] dedicates several chapters to thinning. The calculus of relations is replaced by a calculus of nondeterministic functions: $ThinBy (\preceq) :: [a] \rightarrow [a]$ is now a multivalued function over lists of candidates. Rules and laws are adapted accordingly.

Thinning by grouping takes a slightly different approach, implicitly representing the pre-order. The set of all candidates is conceptually grouped into subsets such that each of these groups can be covered by a single candidate. The approach requires no additional machinery, neither relations, nor nondeterministic or multivalued functions, nor monads. Indeed, the derivation in Section 5 is a routine application of the Bird–Meertens formalism. Whether *thinning by grouping* may serve as a drop-in replacement for the more elaborate frameworks remains to be seen — we have left this for future work.

References

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- [2] Richard Bird and Jeremy Gibbons. 2020. *Algorithm Design with Haskell*. Cambridge University Press.
- [3] Michael L. Fredman. 1975. On computing the length of longest increasing subsequences. *Discrete Mathematics* 11, 1 (1975), 29–35. doi:10.1016/0012-365X(75)90103-X
- [4] Axel Thue. 1912. Über die gegenseitige Lage gleicher Teile gewisser Zeichenreihen. *Skifter udgivne af Videnskaps-Selskabet i Christiania, Matematisk-Naturvidenskabelig Klasse 1* (1912), 1–67. Reprinted in Thue’s “Selected Mathematical Papers” (Oslo: Universitetsforlaget, 1977), 413–477.

*I think that I shall never see
A poem lovely as a tree.
A tree whose hungry mouth is prest
Against the earth’s sweet flowing breast;
A tree that looks at God all day,
And lifts her leafy arms to pray;
A tree that may in Summer wear
A nest of robins in her hair;
Upon whose bosom snow has lain;
Who intimately lives with rain.
Poems are made by fools like me,
But only God can make a tree.
Trees — Alfred Joyce Kilmer*